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Kluyveromyces marxianus and Bacillus coagulans co-cultivation: efficient co-production of bioethanol and lactic acid from pomegranate peels

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Corresponding Author:	Elia Tomas-Pejo, PhD Instituto IMDEA Energía Móstoles, SPAIN
First Author:	Ekin Demiray
Order of Authors:	Ekin Demiray Cristina González-Fernández Elia Tomás-Pejó, PhD
Abstract:	<p>Lignocellulosic biomass utilization is challenging due to the presence of several carbon sources. Thus, microorganisms with different sugar preferences can be used in co-cultures to overcome this hurdle. This work addressed the simultaneous production of lactic acid (LA) from C5 sugars (i.e. xylose) and bioethanol from C6 (i.e. glucose/fructose) with Bacillus coagulans and Kluyveromyces marxianus, respectively. Sequential inoculation and co-inoculation of microorganisms were also compared. At pH 6, co-inoculation in synthetic media resulted in higher bioethanol (0.51 g/g) and LA (0.98 g/g) yields than sequential inoculation. Furthermore, when using lignocellulosic hydrolysates obtained after enzymatic hydrolysis of 20 % w/w pomegranate peels (PP), 92 % and 98 % of the theoretical maximum bioethanol and LA, respectively, were obtained. This study demonstrated the efficient bioethanol/LA co-generation despite the different optimum fermentation conditions of microorganisms and will pave the way to consider co-cultures for improving process efficiency in lignocellulosic biorefineries.</p>

Dear Editor,

Please find enclosed our short communication “*Kluyveromyces marxianus and Bacillus coagulans co-cultivation: efficient co-production of bioethanol and lactic acid from pomegranate peels*” for publication in Bioresource Technology Reports. This an original work that it is not under consideration in any journal. It was previously submitted to Bioresource Technogy and all authors have agreed to transfer it to Bioresource Technology Reports. This work fits very well with the aim and scope of the journal in the Subject Classification: 30.000 BIOFUELS & BIOREFINERIES (SUB-CLASSIFICATION: 30.020).

The lack of model microorganisms that can utilize a broad range of sugars is a challenging issue for lignocellulose utilization. Thus, this article suggests different co-cultivation strategies of unconventional microorganisms to attain the valorization of pomegranate peels (PPs). To the authors knowledge this is the first time that the suitability of PPs for producing LA has been demonstrated. It is worth mentioning that the proposed strategy, in which two microorganisms were inoculated at the same time resulted in an effective way of valorizing PPs and simultaneously producing bioethanol and LA at very high yields.

Authors are convinced that this work is very oportune and worth to publish in a short communication. The progress that this work makes in the field will pave the way for further developing new strategies for residual biomass conversion into bioenergy and bioproducts. We look forward to your evaluation.

Best regards,

Elia Tomás Pejó

Figure 2

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

the GA must be improved with lesser text and should be more made more meaningful

The GA has been improved. Now it appears with less text and it is more illustrative considering what it is included in the article.

Abstract should be rewritten. Also the broad range of sugars utilising capabilities (as mentioned in abstract) of the microorganisms used in this study should be provided

Abstract has been corrected according to reviewer suggestion. It states that “microorganisms with different sugar preferences” are needed. Abstract indicates now in lines 16-19: “This work addressed the simultaneous production of lactic acid (LA) from C5 sugars (i.e. xylose) and bioethanol from C6 (i.e. glucose/fructose) with *Bacillus coagulans* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus*, respectively”. The ability of consume different sugars is indicated in several parts of the article like lines 46-48: “Despite being a very efficient glucose-fermenting yeast, *K. marxianus* can not convert xylose into bioethanol (Mohd Azhar et al., 2017) which results in an inefficient conversion of lignocellulose.” and lines 49-52: “LA bacteria such as *B. coagulans* can efficiently convert glucose and xylose into optically pure LA which is particularly advantageous for poly-lactic acid (PLA) production”

Objectives of this study are poorly defined in the Introduction

Objectives are now clearly defined in lines 56-58: “In this sense, the main objective of this work was to establish the co-cultivation of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20 to efficiently convert hexoses into bioethanol and xylose into L-LA (L-Lactic Acid) from PP.” and Lines 70-77: “Thus, the current study aimed to convert C6 sugars into bioethanol by *K. marxianus* and analyse the effect of oxygen removal during ethanol production in LA fermentation from xylose by *B. coagulans*. For this, co-inoculation and sequential inoculation of microorganisms were performed taking advantage of the thermotolerant trait of *K. marxianus* that allowed co-cultivation at 45 °C. Optimum pH conditions and inoculation strategy for a co-culture were firstly established in synthetic media. Then, real PP-derived hydrolysates obtained after enzymatic hydrolysis of 10, 15, and 20 %, w/w of PP were used.”

Highlights are very basic and genetic; must contain factual data.

Highlights have been corrected according to reviewer suggestion and include some data and conclusions

Mention the source of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875

The source is now mentioned in line 84: “*K. marxianus* CECT 10875, provided by The Advanced Biofuels and Bioproducts Unit (CIEMAT, Spain)”

How the inoculum size/ration of the two cultures was optimized? Relevant results may be included.

Authors research group has been working with both mentioned microorganisms for many years as it is proved by the high number of publications with these microorganisms. Inoculum sizes were already optimized in previous studies. References are now included to justify the selection of the inoculum size in lines 91 and 102.

Mention the characterization methods of PP used for estimation of cellulose, lignin, hemicellulose, etc.

This information is now included in lines 123-125: “PPs were characterized using the standard methods for determination of structural carbohydrates and lignin (LAP-002, LAP- 003, and LAP- 019) of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)”

l116: xylan (not xylane). Corrected

l118: substrate (not substarte) Corrected

None of the pretreatment, except mechanical one done. Right? Correct. Due to the intrinsic characteristics of PPs, no pretreatment was performed which is indeed very positive for the process avoiding the generation of inhibitors.

More details about enzymatic hydrolysis should be provided, like final/working volume, rpm, etc. How mixing problems in 20% S/L were addressed?

Missing information is now included in lines 129-131. “Enzymatic hydrolysis of PP at 10, 15, and 20 % w/w substrate loading was performed in 250-mL shake flasks with 100 mL working volume at 50 °C, 180 rpm and pH 5. This resulted in three PP hydrolysates.”.

Contrary to what it was expected and it was reviewed by the leading author in (see Lignocellulosic ethanol production at high-gravity: challenges and perspectives. Koppram et al 2015. Trends in Biotechnology) 20% w/w substrate loading of PP did not result in mixing problems and only a slight delay in liquefaction was observed. Due to their composition and characteristics, PP behave differently that most common lignocellulosic feedstocks (e.g. wheat straw, barley straw, olive tree pruning, etc.)

How enzyme dosage was fixed for various enzymes?

Enzyme dosages were selected according to previous reports as indicated now in line 135.

What were the concentrations of the various sugars in PP enzyme hydrolysates?

Concentrations of sugars are indicated in figure 3. Due to the limited space to present this work as short communication authors decided to omit this information in the text.

Conclusion section must contain some factual data.

Conclusion section has been rewritten and data have been added in lines 273-275.

What was the basis of coculture. How do the results of lactic acid and ethanol fermentation differ with respect to individual/pure cultures? How does lactic acid bacteria promote growth of yeast in this study? Data should be provided.

Keeping in mind that this is a short communication and not a full article, authors consider that most of the information requested is now included in the text in lines 260-264: “Bioethanol and LA yields obtained in this study are in the range, or even slightly higher, than those previously obtained by *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20 when individually used for bioethanol of LA from lignocellulose (Tomás-Pejó et al., 2009; Cubas-Cano et al.,2020b). Thus, demonstrating that the proposed co-cultivation strategy is an efficient way to simultaneously target several bioproducts”. Lines 210-214: “A recent study reported that *Lactobacillus plantarum* increased the ethanol tolerance of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by promoting the expression of trehalose, ergosterol, proton pumps and stress response transcriptional activators (He et al., 2021). Another report showed that *Lactobacillus amylovorus* provided acetaldehyde that favored the growth rate and bioethanol production of *S. cerevisiae* (Senne de Oliveira Lino et al., 2021)”. In the same line, *K. marxianus* could provide growth factors and bioactive compounds to the LA bacteria resulting in enhanced LA fermentation (Plessas et

al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2017). All these studies have already exemplified the success of co-inoculation of microorganisms supporting that the benefits are not only related to the carbon sources' complementarities”

How oxygen depletion was studied?

This information is included in line 145: “Gas composition (*i.e.*, oxygen level) in the clamped flasks was determined according to Cubas-Cabo et al., (2019b)”

Provide the basis of calculations used for determining yield of ethanol/lactic acid in methodology section

This information has been included in methodology section. Lines 158-161: “Bioethanol yield (g/g) was defined as the concentration of produced bioethanol (g/L) divided by the consumed glucose (g/L) (in case of synthetic media) or the sum of consumed glucose and fructose (g/L) (in case of PP hydrolysate fermentation). LA yield (g/g) was defined as the concentration of produced LA (g/L) divided by consumed xylose (g/g).

l220: put space between words 'attainmaximum' corrected

Which sugar in hydrolysate and synthetic media were used for ethanol and which one for lactic acid fermentation by yeast and bacteria, respectively.

This information is now included in several parts of the article. See lines 16-18: “This work addressed the simultaneous production of lactic acid (LA) from C5 sugars (*i.e.* xylose) and bioethanol from C6 (*i.e.* glucose/fructose) with *Bacillus coagulans* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus*, respectively. Sequential inoculation and co-inoculation of microorganisms were also compared”. Lines 45-46: “Despite being a very efficient glucose-fermenting yeast, *K. marxianus* can not convert xylose into bioethanol (Mohd Azhar et al., 2017) which results in an inefficient conversion of lignocellulose”. Lines 56-58: the main objective of this work was to establish the co-cultivation of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20 to efficiently convert hexoses into bioethanol and xylose into L-LA (L-Lactic Acid) from PP. Lines 70-72: Thus, the current study aimed to convert C6 sugars into bioethanol by *K. marxianus* and analyse the effect of oxygen removal during ethanol production in LA fermentation from xylose by *B. coagulans*.

On observing the ethanol/lactic acid data, efficiencies of more than 90% seems miscalculated/overhyped? Check calculations and provide the basis for the same in methodology section.

Data have been checked and calculations are now provided in methodology section in Lines 158-161: “Bioethanol yield (g/g) was defined as the concentration of produced bioethanol (g/L) divided by the consumed glucose (g/L) (in case of synthetic media) or the sum of consumed glucose and fructose (g/L) (in case of PP hydrolysate fermentation). LA yield (g/g) was defined as the concentration of produced LA (g/L) divided by consumed xylose (g/g).” Despite being very high, these yields are in the range of what was previously observed in other studies with the same microorganisms. See lines 160-165: Bioethanol and LA yields obtained in this study are in the range, or even slightly higher, than those previously obtained by *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20 when individually used for bioethanol or LA from lignocellulose (Tomás-Pejó et al., 2009; Cubas-Cano et al., 2020b). Thus, demonstrating that the proposed co-cultivation strategy is an efficient way to simultaneously target several bioproducts. Lines 243-246: In this sense, bioethanol yield was 0.41 ± 0.02 g/g from 10%-H and increased to 0.47 ± 0.01 g/g

when fermenting 15%-H and 20%-H resulting in 92.7% of the theoretical maximum bioethanol considering both consumed glucose and fructose.

Reviewer #3: The manuscript describes an interesting study on the simultaneous production of lactic acid and bioethanol using sequential inoculation, and co-inoculation of *Kluyveromyces marxianus* CECT 10875, and *Bacillus coagulans* A20 from pomegranate peels. Both processes were evaluated under three different pH values. The efficiency of bioethanol/lactic acid co-generation of both processes was compared. The topic is relevant for both scientific and industrial applications. In my opinion, the manuscript could be published after minor revision:

a) Page 2, line 52 : the term sugar preferencues is not correct. [This sentence has been removed](#)

b) Page 2, line 55: The acronym L-LA was first utilized, and it was not previously defined. [Corrected](#)

c) Page 4, line 80 and line 98: The meaning of the terms YPDA and YPDX should be defined. [Corrected](#)

d) Page 6, line 131, 133, 134, 135: All sentences in these lines should be in the same paragraph. [Corrected](#)

e) Page 7, line 152-153: It is stated that the oxygen presence was high at the initial hours of the process as seen in Fig. 1a, c, and e. However, Fig 1a, c, and e do not show oxygen depletion. The authors should include the oxygen depletion in the Figure 1, or elaborate on the behavior of oxygen concentration through the process.

[Oxygen was not continuously controlled during the fermentation. It was measured 4 h after *K. marxianus* inoculation. It is indicated now in lines 194-198: "Oxygen was depleted in all cases \(co-inoculation and sequential inoculation\) 4 h after *K. marxianus* inoculation. This unexpected very quick oxygen depletion, favored *B. coagulans* to produce LA very rapidly also when co-inoculated with *K. marxianus* and showed a delay in *B. coagulans* addition was not needed for favor LA production."](#)

f) Page 7, line 157: the term concentration pf 9.1 is not correct. [Corrected](#)

g) Page 7, line 161: It is stated that Fig. 1 shows that there were no differences in the LA yields when pH was changed from 5 to 7. However, Fig. 1 does not show the values of LA yields. [Fig. 1a, c, and e were cited in the text after "LA concentration" since they were only referring to that values and not LA yields. In any case, to avoid misunderstanding, specific for LA concentration are now included in the text in lines 174-177: "However, independently of the pH, as no differences were observed in the maximum LA concentration \(from 16.9±0.7 g/L to 17.2±0.1 g/L\) and yields \(from 0.98±0.04 g/g to 0.99±<0.01 g/g\) pointing at yeast being more susceptible to different process pH than bacteria.](#)

h) Page 8 line 178-179: I was unable to see the oxygen depletion in the Figure 1. [Oxygen levels are not included in the figure as indicated in previous comments. However, it is mentioned several times in the text that oxygen was completely depleted after 4 h of fermentation.](#)

i) Page 9, line 213: The term foo bioethanol and LA production is not correct. [Corrected](#)

- Bioethanol/LA were co-produced despite different fermentation conditions of strains
- LA and bioethanol yields higher than 90% were achieved from PP in co-culture
- The inoculation strategy has an effect on both LA and bioethanol production.
- Co-inoculation was more favorable in bioethanol/LA co-production in synthetic media.
- Very high LA (0.98 ± 0.05 g/g) was achieved from xylose derived from PP

1 ***Kluyveromyces marxianus* and *Bacillus coagulans* co-cultivation: efficient co-production**
2 **of bioethanol and lactic acid from pomegranate peels**

3
4 **Demiray E^{1,2}, González-Fernández C^{1,3,4}, Tomás-Pejó E¹.**

5 ¹ Biotechnological Processes Unit, IMDEA Energy, Avda. Ramón de la Sagra 3, 28935
6 Móstoles, Spain

7 ² Medical Laboratory Techniques Department, Health Services Vocational High Scholl,
8 Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, 06760, Çubuk, Ankara, Turke

9 ³ Department of Chemical Engineering and Environmental Technology, School of Industrial
10 Engineering, University of Valladolid, Dr. Mergelina, s/n, Valladolid, 47011, Spain

11 ⁴ Institute of Sustainable Processes, Dr. Mergelina, s/n, Valladolid, 47011, Spain

12 *corresponding author: elia.tomas@imdea.org

13 **Abstract**

14 Lignocellulosic biomass utilization is challenging due to the presence of several carbon
15 sources. Thus, microorganisms with different sugar preferences can be used in co-cultures to
16 overcome this hurdle. This work addressed the simultaneous production of lactic acid (LA)
17 from C5 sugars (i.e. xylose) and bioethanol from C6 (i.e. glucose/fructose) with *Bacillus*
18 *coagulans* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus*, respectively. Sequential inoculation and co-
19 inoculation of microorganisms were also compared. At pH 6, co-inoculation in synthetic
20 media resulted in higher bioethanol (0.51 g/g) and LA (0.98 g/g) yields than sequential
21 inoculation. Furthermore, when using lignocellulosic hydrolysates obtained after enzymatic
22 hydrolysis of 20 % w/w pomegranate peels (PP), 92 % and 98 % of the theoretical maximum
23 bioethanol and LA, respectively, were obtained. This study demonstrated the efficient
24 bioethanol/LA co-generation despite the different optimum fermentation conditions of
25 microorganisms and will pave the way to consider co-cultures for improving process
26 efficiency in lignocellulosic biorefineries.

27 **Keywords:** Pomegranate peel, bioethanol, lactic acid, *Kluyveromyces marxianus*, *Bacillus*
28 *coagulans*, co-inoculation

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Lignocellulosic biomass is the most abundant and cheapest renewable raw material on
31 Earth and is formed by lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose. Hemicellulose contains pentoses
32 such as xylose, and cellulose has a glucose backbone. On the other hand, lignin is a
33 recalcitrant polymer that creates a physical barrier to enzymatic and microbial attacks.
34 Thereby, potentially fermentable sugars present in the lignocellulose can only be obtained
35 after hydrolysis of cellulose and hemicellulose.

36 Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) is a popular fruit consumed worldwide. It has been
37 reported to produce antiviral, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects on
38 consumers (Viuda-Martos et al., 2021). Around 50 % of the total weight of the fruit can result
39 in pomegranate peels (PP) after its processing. These PP contain high organic matter (mainly
40 sugars) and high-water content. Thus, PP disposal creates a significant risk to the environment
41 (Goula and Lazarides, 2015). Due to their traits, PP may be a source of polyphenols and
42 polysaccharides for biofuels and bioproducts (Zhu et al., 2015; Rajha et al., 2019).

43 Bioethanol is a widely available biofuel that can be produced via sugar fermentation
44 with yeasts to replace gasoline total or partially. *Kluyveromyces marxianus* is one of the most
45 interesting yeast species for bioethanol production due to its fast growth rate and
46 thermotolerance (Leonel et al., 2021). Despite being a very efficient glucose-fermenting yeast,
47 *K. marxianus* can not convert xylose into bioethanol (Mohd Azhar et al., 2017) which results
48 in an inefficient conversion of lignocellulose.

49 On the other hand, facultative anaerobic LA bacteria such as *B. coagulans* can
50 efficiently convert glucose and xylose into optically pure LA which is particularly
51 advantageous for poly-lactic acid (PLA) production. This PLA has multiple applications in
52 the plastic, food, medicine, and chemical sectors (Cubas-Cano et al., 2018).

53 A recent study has exemplified the importance of joint production in biorefineries by
54 combining bioethanol and ethyl lactate production (González-Contreras et al., 2023) and

55 suggested a greener integration by producing LA from the biomass as aimed in the current
56 investigation. In this sense, the main objective of this work was to establish the co-cultivation
57 of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20 to efficiently convert hexoses into
58 bioethanol and xylose into L-LA (L-Lactic Acid) from PP. This strategy will result in the
59 complete valorization of the cellulosic and hemicellulosic fractions of this feedstock.

60 However, when different microorganisms are involved in a bioprocess, conditions may
61 be carefully tuned to specific requirements of participant species. Besides, changes in process
62 pH, dissolved oxygen, etc. may be considered to get a stable co-culture. In this sense, oxygen
63 presence is a critical factor for LA and bioethanol co-production. Some yeasts can produce
64 bioethanol when oxygen is present (Dai et al., 2018), but anaerobic conditions are required by
65 most of the LA producers (Zhou et al., 2013; Cubas-Cano et al., 2019a). Due to these hurdles,
66 previous studies targeting at bioethanol and LA production have focused on sequential
67 processes (Wang et al., 2018; Cubas-Cano et al., 2020a; Singh et al., 2022) and little attention
68 has been given to the benefits of co-culturing.

69 Oxygen depletion in alcoholic fermentation could create an anaerobic environment
70 and promote LA production. Thus, the current study aimed to convert C6 sugars into
71 bioethanol by *K. marxianus* and analyse the effect of oxygen removal during ethanol
72 production in LA fermentation from xylose by *B. coagulans*. For this, co-inoculation and
73 sequential inoculation of microorganisms were performed taking advantage of the
74 thermotolerant trait of *K. marxianus* that allowed co-cultivation at 45 °C.

75 Optimum pH conditions and inoculation strategy for a co-culture were firstly established in
76 synthetic media. Then, real PP-derived hydrolysates obtained after enzymatic hydrolysis of
77 10, 15, and 20 %, w/w of PP were used. Despite the production of bioethanol from PP being
78 addressed in previous reports (Talekar et al., 2018; Mazaheri and Ahi, 2021; Saleem et al.,
79 2022), this is the first investigation in which PP was also used for LA production. In this line,

80 this work addresses a novel approach for the simultaneous co-production of LA and
81 bioethanol from PPs by means of co-cultures.

82 **2. Materials and methods**

83 *2.1 Source of microorganisms and preculturing*

84 *K. marxianus* CECT 10875, provided by The Advanced Biofuels and Bioproducts
85 Unit (CIEMAT, Spain), was maintained in YPDA (Yeast, Peptone, Dextrose Agar) (10 g/L
86 yeast extract, 20 g/L peptone, 20 g/L dextrose, and 20 g/L agar) medium at 4 °C. For
87 preinoculum preparation, one colony of cells was inoculated into 100 mL YPD medium (same
88 composition as indicated previously without agar). Flasks were incubated overnight at 42 °C
89 and 150 rpm. After preculture, media were centrifuged at 4000 rpm at 4 °C for 5 min.
90 Supernatant was discarded and obtained cell pellet was resuspended in small volume of sterile
91 distilled water to reach 1 g/L cell dry weight of inoculum as previously used for bioethanol
92 production with the same yeast strain (Tomás-Pejó et al., 2009, 2017).

93 *Bacillus coagulans* A20, supplied by the Bioengineering Department of Leibniz
94 Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB/Potsdam, Germany) was
95 previously evolved to tolerate high ethanol concentrations (Cubas-Cano et al., 2020a) and
96 kept in 30 % glycerol stocks at -80 °C. A small aliquot of cells was taken from the stock (0.5
97 mL) and inoculated into 120-mL clamped flasks containing 50 mL of modified Man, Rogosa,
98 and Sharpe medium as indicated by (Cubas-Cano et al, 2020a). Preinoculum was grown
99 overnight at 52 °C and 150 rpm in anaerobiosis. Filtered helium at 0.5 bar were flushed into
100 the 120-mL clamped flasks around 2 min to reach the anaerobic conditions. Remaining air in
101 the clamped flasks was expelled with a gas outlet. Fermentation experiments were inoculated
102 with 5% (v/v) of inoculum size as indicated in previous reports with the same bacterial strain
103 (Cubas-Cano et al., 2020b).

104 *2.2 Bioethanol and LA co-production in synthetic media*

105 YPDX (Yeast, Peptone, Dextrose, Xylose) (10 g/L yeast extract, 20 g/L peptone, 20
106 g/L glucose, and 20 g/L xylose) medium was firstly used for bioethanol and LA co-
107 production. Fermentation tests were run in triplicates at pH 5, 6, and 7, 45 °C and 150 rpm in
108 120-mL clamped bottles containing 50 mL of working volume. CaCO₃ (20 g/L) was added to
109 maintain the pH. Samples were collected at 1, 2, 4, 18, 24, 48, and 72 h for sugar, xylitol,
110 bioethanol, and LA determination.

111 For co-inoculation of microorganisms, *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans*
112 A20 were added to the fermentation broth at the same time. For sequential inoculation, *B.*
113 *coagulans* A20 was inoculated 18 h after *K. marxianus* inoculation.

114 2.3 *K. marxianus* drop tests when co-cultured with *B. coagulans*

115 *K. marxianus* grown in YPDX medium alone or in a co-inoculture with *B. coagulans*
116 was plated in drop tests on YPDA. Samples were serially diluted with 0.9 % NaCl. Two
117 different inoculation volumes (5 µL and 10 µL) were used and plates were incubated for 48 h
118 at 45 °C. *B. coagulans* cells grown in mMRS without *K. marxinaus* were also plated on
119 YPDA and no growth was observed in 48 h (data not shown) indicating that observed
120 colonies were only *K. marxianus*.

121 2.4 Enzymatic hydrolysis of PP and subsequent fermentation for bioethanol/LA co-production

122 PP were dried and milled (particle size 2000-4000 µm) in a laboratory-type mill
123 (Retsch, SM 2000, Germany) before characterization. PP were characterized using the
124 standard methods for determination of structural carbohydrates and lignin (LAP-002, LAP-
125 003, and LAP- 019) of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL). It had the
126 following composition (% w/w): 15.8±0.5 cellulose; 4.4±0.2 xylan; 1.7±<0.1 galactan;
127 2.3±0.1 arabinan; 0.4±<0.1 mannan; 1.5±<0.1 acetyl groups and 21.3±0.3 acid insoluble
128 lignin.

129 Enzymatic hydrolysis of PP at 10, 15, and 20 % w/w substrate loading was performed
130 in 250-mL shake flasks with 100 mL working volume at 50 °C, 180 rpm and pH 5. This
131 resulted in three PP hydrolysates. Celluclast 1.5 L (60 FPU/mL, Novozymes, Denmark), β -
132 glucosidase (600 IU/mL, Novozymes, Denmark), CellicHtec2 (300 IU/mg, Novozymes,
133 Denmark) and β -xylosidase (118 IU/mg, Megazyme/Ireland) were added at 15 FPU/g
134 substrate, 15 IU/g substrate, 50 IU/mg substrate, and 0.1 IU/mg substrate, respectively as
135 indicated by (Cubas-Cano et al., 2020c; Moreno et al., 2022). After hydrolysis, PP media
136 were centrifuged and the supernatant was filtered with 0.22 μ m membrane filter to obtain PP
137 hydrolysates for the fermentation experiments.

138 *K. marxianus* and *B. coagulans* were co-inoculated in PP hydrolysates at the same
139 inoculum sizes indicated for synthetic media. Experiments were carried out in 120-mL
140 clamped flask containing 50 mL of media at pH 6, 45 °C and 150 rpm. Samples were
141 withdrawn at 1, 2, 4, 18, 24, 48, 72, and 120 h and analyzed by HPLC for sugar and product
142 determination. CaCO₃ (20 g/L) was used to maintain the pH along fermentation.

143 *2.5 Analytical methods and calculations*

144 PP were characterised according to the National Renewable Energy Laboratory/NREL
145 protocols (LAP-001, LAP-002, LAP-003, LAP-004, LAP-017, and LAP-019). Gas
146 composition (*i.e.*, oxygen level) in the clamped flasks was determined according to Cubas-
147 Cabo et al., (2019b).

148 Before analyses, fermentation samples were centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 5 min. The
149 supernatant was taken to another centrifuge tube and was purified with the Carrez clarification
150 kit (Merck, HC160131). After the second centrifugation, the supernatant was filtered through
151 0.22 μ m membrane filters (Thermo Scientific® Nylon 0.2 μ m). Glucose, xylose, fructose, LA,
152 xylitol, acetic acid and bioethanol were quantified by an HPLC system (Agilent) with an
153 aminex HPX-87H column (Bio-Rad Labs, Hercules, CA) according to Cubas-Cano et al.,

154 (2018). Since xylose and fructose can not be separated in this column, sugar determination in
155 PP enzymatic hydrolysis and during PP hydrolysates fermentation was determined in
156 CarboSep CHO 682 column (Teknokroma) at 80 °C with ultrapure water as a mobile phase
157 and flow rate of 0.4 mL/min.

158 Bioethanol yield (g/g) was defined as the concentration of produced bioethanol (g/L) divided
159 by the consumed glucose (g/L) (in case if synthetic media) or the sum of consumed glucose
160 and fructose (g/L) (in case of PP hydrolysate fermentation). LA yield (g/g) was defined as the
161 concentration of produced LA (g/L) divided by consumed xylose (g/g).

162 **3. Results and discussion**

163 *3.1 Co-inoculation and sequential inoculation strategies for bioethanol and LA co-production* 164 *in synthetic media at different pH*

165 pH values of 4-6 are optimum for the yeasts (*i.e.*, *K. marxianus*) while pH 5.5-6.5 are
166 optimum pH for the LA bacteria. In this sense, pH optimization is a crucial step when several
167 microorganisms are grown in a co-culture.

168 As shown in Fig. 1., when both microorganisms were co-inoculated, negligible
169 amounts of LA were detected at very initial hours of the processes while the oxygen presence
170 was still high (Fig. 1a, c, and e). LA concentrations increased after oxygen depletion at around
171 4 h and reached its maximum level at 18-24 h of process when xylose depletion took place
172 with no significant differences at different pHs. By contrast, the maximum bioethanol
173 concentration of 9.1 ± 0.8 g/L was reached at pH 6 resulting in a nearly 100 % of the
174 theoretical maximum. Bioethanol concentration significantly decreased to 7.1 ± 0.4 g/L and
175 7.7 ± 0.3 g/L when pH was 5 and 7, respectively. However, independently of the pH, as no
176 differences were observed in the maximum LA concentration (from 16.9 ± 0.7 g/L to 17.2 ± 0.1
177 g/L) and yields (from 0.98 ± 0.04 g/g to $0.99 \pm < 0.01$ g/g) pointing at yeast being more
178 susceptible to different process pH than bacteria.

179 In sequential inoculation, the lowest bioethanol concentration and yield (7.2 ± 0.2 g/L
180 and 0.81 ± 0.03 g/g, respectively) were attained at pH 5 (Fig. 1b) and no significant differences
181 in bioethanol titers were observed when comparing pH 6 and pH 7 (Fig. 1d, f). However,
182 contrary to what was observed in case of co-inoculation, process pH also had a significant
183 effect on LA production and yields. More specifically, a maximum LA concentration and
184 yield of 16.0 ± 0.2 g/L and 0.92 ± 0.02 g/g, respectively were reached at pH 6. These values
185 significantly decreased to 14.1 ± 0.5 g/L and 0.81 ± 0.03 g/g at pH 5 and to 14.0 ± 0.7 g/L and
186 0.81 ± 0.03 g/g at pH 7. This fact clearly showed that the inoculation strategy had an effect on
187 both LA and bioethanol production. Furthermore, when microorganisms were co-inoculated,
188 LA production was significantly higher than that in sequential inoculation.

189 Since anaerobic conditions favor LA fermentation (Cubas-Cano et al., 2019a),
190 sequential inoculation was expected to promote LA production due to the reduction in oxygen
191 pressure when bioethanol was produced by *K. marxianus*. Notwithstanding, in the present
192 study, LA concentrations at 54 h of fermentation when both microorganisms were co-
193 inoculated were always higher than that at 72 h of process in sequential inoculation (54 h after
194 *B. coagulans* addition) (Fig. 1). Oxygen was depleted in all cases (co-inoculation and
195 sequential inoculation) 4 h after *K. marxianus* inoculation. This unexpected very quick
196 oxygen depletion, favored *B. coagulans* to produce LA very rapidly also when co-inoculated
197 with *K. marxianus* and showed a delay in *B. coagulans* addition was not needed for favor LA
198 production.

199 In case of sequential inoculation, a slight consumption of xylose by *K. marxianus* was
200 observed before *B. coagulans* addition (Fig. 1b, d and f). Some *K. marxianus* strains can
201 consume and convert xylose into xylitol (Kumar et al., 2009). In this study, despite being very
202 low, xylitol concentration was slightly higher in sequential inoculation (1.6 ± 0.1 g/L) than in
203 co-inoculation (1.2 ± 0.1 g/L) at all tested pH. This fact implied lower availability of xylose for

204 LA production in the sequential strategy, ultimately resulting in lower LA concentration and
205 yields when inoculation of *B. coagulans* was delayed.

206 As a matter of fact, co-inoculation was the most favorable strategy for bioethanol and
207 LA co-generation. The higher product yields and titers in co-inoculation could also be
208 explained by synergistic interactions between microorganisms at the early stages of
209 fermentation.

210 A recent study reported that *Lactobacillus plantarum* increased the ethanol tolerance
211 of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by promoting the expression of trehalose, ergosterol, proton
212 pumps and stress response transcriptional activators (He et al., 2021). Another report showed
213 that *Lactobacillus amylovorus* provided acetaldehyde that favored the growth rate and
214 bioethanol production of *S. cerevisiae* (Senne de Oliveira Lino et al., 2021). In the same line,
215 *K. marxianus* could provide growth factors and bioactive compounds to the LA bacteria
216 resulting in enhanced LA fermentation (Plessas et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2017). All these
217 studies have already exemplified the success of co-inoculation of microorganisms supporting
218 that the benefits are not only related to the carbon sources' complementarities.

219 In this investigation, the positive effect that *B. coagulans* A20 presence had on *K.*
220 *marxianus* CECT 10875 was also revealed with different drop tests. As it shown in Fig. 2.,
221 yeast growth on plates was more pronounced in samples taken from *K. marxianus* and *B.*
222 *coagulans* co-cultivation (Km+Bc) when compared with single *K. marxianus* culture (Km).
223 This effect was more evident with the lowest drop volume (5 μ L) and at the highest dilution
224 (10^{-7}) suggesting a synergistic positive effect on both microorganisms when co-inoculated.

225 All these findings pointed at co-inoculation of yeast and bacteria as a beneficial
226 strategy for bioethanol/LA co-generation. Thus, co-inoculation of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875
227 and *B. coagulans* A20 was selected for fermentation experiments of PP hydrolysates at pH 6.

228 *3.2 Bioethanol/LA co-generation from PP derived-hydrolysates*

229 The hydrolysates obtained in enzymatic hydrolysis of PP at 10, 15, and 20 % w/w of
230 substrate loadings (named 10%-H, 15%-H and 20%-H) were used for bioethanol and LA
231 production at pH 6 with co-inoculation of *K. marxianus* and *B. coagulans*. 10%-H, 15%-H
232 and 20%-H contained 41.2 g/L, 62.9 g/L and 84.6 g/L of total sugars, respectively.

233 The time courses of bioethanol and LA co-production from PP hydrolysates are
234 shown in Fig. 3. In case of 10%-H, glucose was not detected after 24 h of the process (Fig.
235 3a). On the other hand, with 15%-H and 20%-H, glucose was exhausted at 48 h and 72 h,
236 respectively. When fermenting 10%-H and 15%-H, the maximum bioethanol and LA
237 concentrations were obtained at 48 h while 120 h were needed to attain maximum LA and
238 bioethanol concentrations in 20%-H (Fig. 3c). These prolonged fermentation time and delayed
239 sugar exhaustion were result of the higher sugar concentration in 20%-H when compared with
240 10%-H and 15%-H.

241 In 10%-H, 13.7 ± 1.0 g/L bioethanol and 5.5 ± 0.2 g/L LA were produced, respectively.
242 These concentrations increased to 24.6 ± 0.1 g/L and 9.4 ± 0.1 g/L for bioethanol and LA,
243 respectively in 15%-H and to 32.9 ± 2.4 g/L and 15.0 ± 2.0 g/L, when 20%-H was used. In this
244 sense, bioethanol yield was 0.41 ± 0.02 g/g from 10%-H and increased to 0.47 ± 0.01 g/g when
245 fermenting 15%-H and 20%-H resulting in 92.7% of the theoretical maximum bioethanol
246 considering both consumed glucose and fructose. These bioethanol concentrations and yields
247 were significantly higher than those previously reported from PP in which case *S. cerevisiae*
248 produced 12.9 g/L bioethanol when PP loading was 12.8% w/w (Mazaheri et al., 2021). In
249 another study, the bioethanol yield of *Metschnikowia cibodasensis* was 0.41 g/g when acid-
250 pretreated PP was used as a raw material (Saleem et al., 2022).

251 The fermentation of 10%-H and 15%-H resulted in similar LA yields (0.90 ± 0.02 g/g
252 and $0.89 \pm < 0.01$ g/g, respectively) and LA production started at early fermentation times (Fig
253 3a, b). On the other hand, as shown in Fig. 3c, in the fermentation of 20%-H, a slight delay in

254 LA production was observed. In this case, LA production started after 18 h of process
255 concomitantly with xylose consumption by *B. coagulans*. Despite this delay, a very high LA
256 yield was reached in 20%-H fermentation (0.98 ± 0.05 g/g) demonstrating for the first time the
257 suitability of PP for being used as feedstock for LA production. It is worth mentioning that
258 xylitol was negligible at these conditions, indicating that all xylose in the media was diverted
259 for LA production by *B. coagulans*.

260 Bioethanol and LA yields obtained in this study are in the range, or even slightly
261 higher, than those previously obtained by *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20
262 when individually used for bioethanol or LA from lignocellulose (Tomás-Pejó et al., 2009;
263 Cubas-Cano et al., 2020b). Thus, demonstrating that the proposed co-cultivation strategy is an
264 efficient way to simultaneously target several bioproducts. In this sense, these results pointed
265 at the proposed strategy, in which two microorganisms were co-inoculated, as an effective
266 way of valorizing PP and simultaneously producing bioethanol and LA at very high yields.

267 **4. Conclusions**

268 The co-inoculation of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20 resulted in
269 higher bioethanol and LA titers than the sequential inoculation. The expected positive effect
270 of oxygen depletion during bioethanol production on subsequent LA fermentation was not
271 observed. Thus, results pointed at synergistic interactions between microorganisms to explain
272 the beneficial effect of co-inoculation. The efficient bioethanol and LA simultaneous
273 generation from PP were demonstrated reaching 93 % and 98 % of the theoretical maximum
274 bioethanol and LA, respectively.

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368 369 FIGURE CAPTIONS

370 Figure 1. Fermentation of YPDX media with co-inoculation (a, c, e) and sequential inoculation
371 (b, d, f) of *K. marxianus* and *B. coagulans*. pH 5 (a, b), 6 (c, d) and 7 (e, f). The dotted lines
372 show *B. coagulans* inoculation time.

373 Figure 2. Drop tests on YPD plates of samples from *K. marxianus*-*B. coagulans* co-culture (Km
374 + Bc) and *K. marxianus* monoculture (Km) at 120 h of fermentation. A: 5 μ L drops; B: 10 μ L
375 drops

376 Figure 3. Time course of bioethanol and LA co-production with co-inoculated microorganisms
377 in PPs derived hydrolysates from: a) 10 % w/w PPs; b) 15 % w/w PPs c) 20 % w/w PPs.

378

1 ***Kluyveromyces marxianus* and *Bacillus coagulans* co-cultivation: efficient co-production**
2 **of bioethanol and lactic acid from pomegranate peels**

3
4 **Demiray E^{1,2}, González-Fernández C^{1,3,4}, Tomás-Pejó E¹.**

5 ¹ Biotechnological Processes Unit, IMDEA Energy, Avda. Ramón de la Sagra 3, 28935
6 Móstoles, Spain

7 ² Medical Laboratory Techniques Department, Health Services Vocational High Scholl,
8 Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, 06760, Çubuk, Ankara, Turke

9 ³ Department of Chemical Engineering and Environmental Technology, School of Industrial
10 Engineering, University of Valladolid, Dr. Mergelina, s/n, Valladolid, 47011, Spain

11 ⁴ Institute of Sustainable Processes, Dr. Mergelina, s/n, Valladolid, 47011, Spain

12 *corresponding author: elia.tomas@imdea.org

13 **Abstract**

14 **Lignocellulosic biomass utilization is challenging due to the presence of several carbon**
15 **sources.** Thus, microorganisms with different sugar preferences can be used in co-cultures to
16 overcome this hurdle. **This work addressed the simultaneous production of lactic acid (LA)**
17 **from C5 sugars (i.e. xylose) and bioethanol from C6 (i.e. glucose/fructose) with *Bacillus***
18 ***coagulans* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus*, respectively. Sequential inoculation and co-**
19 **inoculation of microorganisms were also compared.** At pH 6, co-inoculation in synthetic
20 media resulted in higher bioethanol (0.51 g/g) and LA (0.98 g/g) yields than sequential
21 inoculation. Furthermore, when using **lignocellulosic** hydrolysates obtained after enzymatic
22 hydrolysis of 20 % w/w pomegranate peels (PP), 92 % and 98 % of the theoretical maximum
23 bioethanol and LA, respectively, were obtained. This study demonstrated the efficient
24 bioethanol/LA co-generation despite the different optimum fermentation conditions of
25 microorganisms and will pave the way to consider co-cultures for improving process
26 efficiency in lignocellulosic biorefineries.

27 **Keywords:** Pomegranate peel, bioethanol, lactic acid, *Kluyveromyces marxianus*, *Bacillus*
28 *coagulans*, co-inoculation

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Lignocellulosic biomass is the most abundant and cheapest renewable raw material on
31 Earth and is formed by lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose. Hemicellulose contains pentoses
32 such as xylose, and cellulose has a glucose backbone. On the other hand, lignin is a
33 recalcitrant polymer that creates a physical barrier to enzymatic and microbial attacks.
34 Thereby, potentially fermentable sugars present in the lignocellulose can only be obtained
35 after hydrolysis of cellulose and hemicellulose.

36 Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) is a popular fruit consumed worldwide. It has been
37 reported to produce antiviral, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects on
38 consumers (Viuda-Martos et al., 2021). Around 50 % of the total weight of the fruit can result
39 in pomegranate peels (PP) after its processing. These PP contain high organic matter (mainly
40 sugars) and high-water content. Thus, PP disposal creates a significant risk to the environment
41 (Goula and Lazarides, 2015). Due to their traits, PP may be a source of polyphenols and
42 polysaccharides for biofuels and bioproducts (Zhu et al., 2015; Rajha et al., 2019).

43 Bioethanol is a widely available biofuel that can be produced via sugar fermentation
44 with yeasts to replace gasoline total or partially. *Kluyveromyces marxianus* is one of the most
45 interesting yeast species for bioethanol production due to its fast growth rate and
46 thermotolerance (Leonel et al., 2021). **Despite being a very efficient glucose-fermenting yeast,**
47 ***K. marxianus* can not convert xylose into bioethanol (Mohd Azhar et al., 2017) which results**
48 **in an inefficient conversion of lignocellulose.**

49 On the other hand, facultative anaerobic LA bacteria such as *B. coagulans* can
50 efficiently convert **glucose and** xylose into optically pure LA which is particularly
51 advantageous for poly-lactic acid (PLA) production. This PLA has multiple applications in
52 the plastic, food, medicine, and chemical sectors (Cubas-Cano et al., 2018).

53 A recent study has exemplified the importance of joint production in biorefineries by
54 combining bioethanol and ethyl lactate production (González-Contreras et al., 2023) and

55 suggested a greener integration by producing LA from the biomass as aimed in the current
56 investigation. In this sense, the main objective of this work was to establish the co-cultivation
57 of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20 to efficiently convert hexoses into
58 bioethanol and xylose into L-LA (L-Lactic Acid) from PP. This strategy will result in the
59 complete valorization of the cellulosic and hemicellulosic fractions of this feedstock.

60 However, when different microorganisms are involved in a bioprocess, conditions may
61 be carefully tuned to specific requirements of participant species. Besides, changes in process
62 pH, dissolved oxygen, etc. may be considered to get a stable co-culture. In this sense, oxygen
63 presence is a critical factor for LA and bioethanol co-production. Some yeasts can produce
64 bioethanol when oxygen is present (Dai et al., 2018), but anaerobic conditions are required by
65 most of the LA producers (Zhou et al., 2013; Cubas-Cano et al., 2019a). Due to these hurdles,
66 previous studies targeting at bioethanol and LA production have focused on sequential
67 processes (Wang et al., 2018; Cubas-Cano et al., 2020a; Singh et al., 2022) and little attention
68 has been given to the benefits of co-culturing.

69 Oxygen depletion in alcoholic fermentation could create an anaerobic environment
70 and promote LA production. Thus, the current study aimed to convert C6 sugars into
71 bioethanol by *K. marxianus* and analyse the effect of oxygen removal during ethanol
72 production in LA fermentation from xylose by *B. coagulans*. For this, co-inoculation and
73 sequential inoculation of microorganisms were performed taking advantage of the
74 thermotolerant trait of *K. marxianus* that allowed co-cultivation at 45 °C.
75 Optimum pH conditions and inoculation strategy for a co-culture were firstly established in
76 synthetic media. Then, real PP-derived hydrolysates obtained after enzymatic hydrolysis of
77 10, 15, and 20 %, w/w of PP were used. Despite the production of bioethanol from PP being
78 addressed in previous reports (Talekar et al., 2018; Mazaheri and Ahi, 2021; Saleem et al.,
79 2022), this is the first investigation in which PP was also used for LA production. In this line,

80 this work addresses a novel approach for the simultaneous co-production of LA and
81 bioethanol from PPs by means of co-cultures.

82 **2. Materials and methods**

83 *2.1 Source of microorganisms and preculturing*

84 *K. marxianus* CECT 10875, provided by **The Advanced Biofuels and Bioproducts**
85 **Unit (CIEMAT, Spain)**, was maintained in YPDA (**Yeast, Peptone, Dextrose Agar**) (10 g/L
86 yeast extract, 20 g/L peptone, 20 g/L dextrose, and 20 g/L agar) medium at 4 °C. For
87 preinoculum preparation, one colony of cells was inoculated into 100 mL YPD medium (same
88 composition as indicated previously without agar). Flasks were incubated overnight at 42 °C
89 and 150 rpm. After preculture, media were centrifuged at 4000 rpm at 4 °C for 5 min.
90 Supernatant was discarded and obtained cell pellet was resuspended in small volume of sterile
91 distilled water to reach 1 g/L cell dry weight of inoculum **as previously used for bioethanol**
92 **production with the same yeast strain (Tomás-Pejó et al., 2009, 2017).**

93 *Bacillus coagulans* A20, supplied by the Bioengineering Department of Leibniz
94 Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB/Potsdam, Germany) was
95 previously evolved to tolerate high ethanol concentrations (Cubas-Cano et al., 2020a) and
96 kept in 30 % glycerol stocks at -80 °C. A small aliquot of cells was taken from the stock (0.5
97 mL) and inoculated into 120-mL clamped flasks containing 50 mL of modified Man, Rogosa,
98 and Sharpe medium as indicated by (Cubas-Cano et al, 2020a). Preinoculum was grown
99 overnight at 52 °C and 150 rpm in anaerobiosis. Filtered helium at 0.5 bar were flushed into
100 the 120-mL clamped flasks around 2 min to reach the anaerobic conditions. Remaining air in
101 the clamped flasks was expelled with a gas outlet. Fermentation experiments were inoculated
102 with 5% (v/v) of inoculum size **as indicated in previous reports with the same bacterial strain**
103 **(Cubas-Cano et al., 2020b).**

104 *2.2 Bioethanol and LA co-production in synthetic media*

105 **YPDX (Yeast, Peptone, Dextrose, Xylose)** (10 g/L yeast extract, 20 g/L peptone, 20
106 g/L glucose, and 20 g/L xylose) medium was firstly used for bioethanol and LA co-
107 production. Fermentation tests were run in triplicates at pH 5, 6, and 7, 45 °C and 150 rpm in
108 120-mL clamped bottles containing 50 mL of working volume. CaCO₃ (20 g/L) was added to
109 maintain the pH. Samples were collected at 1, 2, 4, 18, 24, 48, and 72 h for sugar, xylitol,
110 bioethanol, and LA determination.

111 For co-inoculation of microorganisms, *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans*
112 A20 were added to the fermentation broth at the same time. For sequential inoculation, *B.*
113 *coagulans* A20 was inoculated 18 h after *K. marxianus* inoculation.

114 2.3 *K. marxianus* drop tests when co-cultured with *B. coagulans*

115 *K. marxianus* grown in YPDX medium alone or in a co-inoculture with *B. coagulans*
116 was plated in drop tests on YPDA. Samples were serially diluted with 0.9 % NaCl. Two
117 different inoculation volumes (5 µL and 10 µL) were used and plates were incubated for 48 h
118 at 45 °C. *B. coagulans* cells grown in mMRS without *K. marxianus* were also plated on
119 YPDA and no growth was observed in 48 h (data not shown) indicating that observed
120 colonies were only *K. marxianus*.

121 2.4 Enzymatic hydrolysis of PP and subsequent fermentation for bioethanol/LA co-production

122 PP were dried and milled (particle size 2000-4000 µm) in a laboratory-type mill
123 (Retsch, SM 2000, Germany) before characterization. **PP were characterized using the**
124 **standard methods for determination of structural carbohydrates and lignin (LAP-002, LAP-**
125 **003, and LAP- 019) of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL).** It had the
126 following composition (% w/w): 15.8±0.5 cellulose; 4.4±0.2 xylan; 1.7±<0.1 galactan;
127 2.3±0.1 arabinan; 0.4±<0.1 mannan; 1.5±<0.1 acetyl groups and 21.3±0.3 acid insoluble
128 lignin.

129 Enzymatic hydrolysis of PP at 10, 15, and 20 % w/w **substrate** loading was performed
130 **in 250-mL shake flasks with 100 mL working volume at 50 °C, 180 rpm and pH 5. This**
131 **resulted in three PP hydrolysates.** Celluclast 1.5 L (60 FPU/mL, Novozymes, Denmark), β -
132 glucosidase (600 IU/mL, Novozymes, Denmark), CellicHtec2 (300 IU/mg, Novozymes,
133 Denmark) and β -xylosidase (118 IU/mg, Megazyme/Ireland) were added at 15 FPU/g
134 substrate, 15 IU/g substrate, 50 IU/mg substrate, and 0.1 IU/mg substrate, respectively **as**
135 **indicated by (Cubas-Cano et al., 2020c; Moreno et al., 2022).** After hydrolysis, PP media
136 were centrifuged and the supernatant was filtered with 0.22 μ m membrane filter to obtain PP
137 hydrolysates for the fermentation experiments.

138 *K. marxianus* and *B. coagulans* were co-inoculated in PP hydrolysates at the same
139 inoculum sizes indicated for synthetic media. Experiments were carried out in 120-mL
140 clamped flask containing 50 mL of media at pH 6, 45 °C and 150 rpm. Samples were
141 withdrawn at 1, 2, 4, 18, 24, 48, 72, and 120 h and analyzed by HPLC for sugar and product
142 determination. CaCO₃ (20 g/L) was used to maintain the pH along fermentation.

143 *2.5 Analytical methods and calculations*

144 **PP were characterised according to the National Renewable Energy Laboratory/NREL**
145 **protocols (LAP-001, LAP-002, LAP-003, LAP-004, LAP-017, and LAP-019).** Gas
146 composition (*i.e.*, **oxygen level**) in the clamped flasks was determined according to Cubas-
147 Cabo et al., (2019b).

148 Before analyses, fermentation samples were centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 5 min. The
149 supernatant was taken to another centrifuge tube and was purified with the Carrez clarification
150 kit (Merck, HC160131). After the second centrifugation, the supernatant was filtered through
151 0.22 μ m membrane filters (Thermo Scientific® Nylon 0.2 μ m). Glucose, xylose, fructose, LA,
152 xylitol, acetic acid and bioethanol were quantified by an HPLC system (Agilent) with an
153 aminex HPX-87H column (Bio-Rad Labs, Hercules, CA) according to Cubas-Cano et al.,

154 (2018). Since xylose and fructose can not be separated in this column, sugar determination in
155 PP enzymatic hydrolysis and during PP hydrolysates fermentation was determined in
156 CarboSep CHO 682 column (Teknokroma) at 80 °C with ultrapure water as a mobile phase
157 and flow rate of 0.4 mL/min.

158 Bioethanol yield (g/g) was defined as the concentration of produced bioethanol (g/L) divided
159 by the consumed glucose (g/L) (in case if synthetic media) or the sum of consumed glucose
160 and fructose (g/L) (in case of PP hydrolysate fermentation). LA yield (g/g) was defined as the
161 concentration of produced LA (g/L) divided by consumed xylose (g/g).

162 3. Results and discussion

163 3.1 Co-inoculation and sequential inoculation strategies for bioethanol and LA co-production 164 in synthetic media at different pH

165 pH values of 4-6 are optimum for the yeasts (*i.e.*, *K. marxianus*) while pH 5.5-6.5 are
166 optimum pH for the LA bacteria. In this sense, pH optimization is a crucial step when several
167 microorganisms are grown in a co-culture.

168 As shown in Fig. 1., when both microorganisms were co-inoculated, negligible
169 amounts of LA were detected at very initial hours of the processes while the oxygen presence
170 was still high (Fig. 1a, c, and e). LA concentrations increased after oxygen depletion at around
171 4 h and reached its maximum level at 18-24 h of process when xylose depletion took place
172 with no significant differences at different pHs. By contrast, the maximum bioethanol
173 concentration of 9.1±0.8 g/L was reached at pH 6 resulting in a nearly 100 % of the
174 theoretical maximum. Bioethanol concentration significantly decreased to 7.1±0.4 g/L and
175 7.7±0.3 g/L when pH was 5 and 7, respectively. However, independently of the pH, as no
176 differences were observed in the maximum LA concentration (from 16.9±0.7 g/L to 17.2±0.1
177 g/L) and yields (from 0.98±0.04 g/g to 0.99±<0.01 g/g) pointing at yeast being more
178 susceptible to different process pH than bacteria.

179 In sequential inoculation, the lowest bioethanol concentration and yield (7.2 ± 0.2 g/L
180 and 0.81 ± 0.03 g/g, respectively) were attained at pH 5 (Fig. 1b) and no significant differences
181 in bioethanol titers were observed when comparing pH 6 and pH 7 (Fig. 1d, f). However,
182 contrary to what was observed in case of co-inoculation, process pH also had a significant
183 effect on LA production and yields. More specifically, a maximum LA concentration and
184 yield of 16.0 ± 0.2 g/L and 0.92 ± 0.02 g/g, respectively were reached at pH 6. These values
185 significantly decreased to 14.1 ± 0.5 g/L and 0.81 ± 0.03 g/g at pH 5 and to 14.0 ± 0.7 g/L and
186 0.81 ± 0.03 g/g at pH 7. This fact clearly showed that the inoculation strategy had an effect on
187 both LA and bioethanol production. Furthermore, when microorganisms were co-inoculated,
188 LA production was significantly higher than that in sequential inoculation.

189 Since anaerobic conditions favor LA fermentation (Cubas-Cano et al., 2019a),
190 sequential inoculation was expected to promote LA production due to the reduction in oxygen
191 pressure when bioethanol was produced by *K. marxianus*. Notwithstanding, in the present
192 study, LA concentrations at 54 h of fermentation when both microorganisms were co-
193 inoculated were always higher than that at 72 h of process in sequential inoculation (54 h after
194 *B. coagulans* addition) (Fig. 1). Oxygen was depleted in all cases (co-inoculation and
195 sequential inoculation) 4 h after *K. marxianus* inoculation. This unexpected very quick
196 oxygen depletion, favored *B. coagulans* to produce LA very rapidly also when co-inoculated
197 with *K. marxianus* and showed a delay in *B. coagulans* addition was not needed for favor LA
198 production.

199 In case of sequential inoculation, a slight consumption of xylose by *K. marxianus* was
200 observed before *B. coagulans* addition (Fig. 1b, d and f). Some *K. marxianus* strains can
201 consume and convert xylose into xylitol (Kumar et al., 2009). In this study, despite being very
202 low, xylitol concentration was slightly higher in sequential inoculation (1.6 ± 0.1 g/L) than in
203 co-inoculation (1.2 ± 0.1 g/L) at all tested pH. This fact implied lower availability of xylose for

204 LA production in the sequential strategy, ultimately resulting in lower LA concentration and
205 yields when inoculation of *B. coagulans* was delayed.

206 As a matter of fact, co-inoculation was the most favorable strategy for bioethanol and
207 LA co-generation. The higher product yields and titers in co-inoculation could also be
208 explained by synergistic interactions between microorganisms at the early stages of
209 fermentation.

210 A recent study reported that *Lactobacillus plantarum* increased the ethanol tolerance
211 of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by promoting the expression of trehalose, ergosterol, proton
212 pumps and stress response transcriptional activators (He et al., 2021). Another report showed
213 that *Lactobacillus amylovorus* provided acetaldehyde that favored the growth rate and
214 bioethanol production of *S. cerevisiae* (Senne de Oliveira Lino et al., 2021). In the same line,
215 *K. marxianus* could provide growth factors and bioactive compounds to the LA bacteria
216 resulting in enhanced LA fermentation (Plessas et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2017). All these
217 studies have already exemplified the success of co-inoculation of microorganisms supporting
218 that the benefits are not only related to the carbon sources' complementarities.

219 In this investigation, the positive effect that *B. coagulans* A20 presence had on *K.*
220 *marxianus* CECT 10875 was also revealed with different drop tests. As it shown in Fig. 2.,
221 yeast growth on plates was more pronounced in samples taken from *K. marxianus* and *B.*
222 *coagulans* co-cultivation (Km+Bc) when compared with single *K. marxianus* culture (Km).
223 This effect was more evident with the lowest drop volume (5 μ L) and at the highest dilution
224 (10^{-7}) suggesting a synergistic positive effect on both microorganisms when co-inoculated.

225 All these findings pointed at co-inoculation of yeast and bacteria as a beneficial
226 strategy for bioethanol/LA co-generation. Thus, co-inoculation of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875
227 and *B. coagulans* A20 was selected for fermentation experiments of PP hydrolysates at pH 6.

228 *3.2 Bioethanol/LA co-generation from PP derived-hydrolysates*

229 The hydrolysates obtained in enzymatic hydrolysis of PP at 10, 15, and 20 % w/w of
230 substrate loadings (named 10%-H, 15%-H and 20%-H) were used for bioethanol and LA
231 production at pH 6 with co-inoculation of *K. marxianus* and *B. coagulans*. 10%-H, 15%-H
232 and 20%-H contained 41.2 g/L, 62.9 g/L and 84.6 g/L of total sugars, respectively.

233 The time courses of bioethanol and LA co-production from PP hydrolysates are
234 shown in Fig. 3. In case of 10%-H, glucose was not detected after 24 h of the process (Fig.
235 3a). On the other hand, with 15%-H and 20%-H, glucose was exhausted at 48 h and 72 h,
236 respectively. When fermenting 10%-H and 15%-H, the maximum bioethanol and LA
237 concentrations were obtained at 48 h while 120 h were needed to attain maximum LA and
238 bioethanol concentrations in 20%-H (Fig. 3c). These prolonged fermentation time and delayed
239 sugar exhaustion were result of the higher sugar concentration in 20%-H when compared with
240 10%-H and 15%-H.

241 In 10%-H, 13.7 ± 1.0 g/L bioethanol and 5.5 ± 0.2 g/L LA were produced, respectively.
242 These concentrations increased to 24.6 ± 0.1 g/L and 9.4 ± 0.1 g/L for bioethanol and LA,
243 respectively in 15%-H and to 32.9 ± 2.4 g/L and 15.0 ± 2.0 g/L, when 20%-H was used. In this
244 sense, bioethanol yield was 0.41 ± 0.02 g/g from 10%-H and increased to 0.47 ± 0.01 g/g when
245 fermenting 15%-H and 20%-H resulting in 92.7% of the theoretical maximum bioethanol
246 considering both consumed glucose and fructose. These bioethanol concentrations and yields
247 were significantly higher than those previously reported from PP in which case *S. cerevisiae*
248 produced 12.9 g/L bioethanol when PP loading was 12.8% w/w (Mazaheri et al., 2021). In
249 another study, the bioethanol yield of *Metschnikowia cibodasensis* was 0.41 g/g when acid-
250 pretreated PP was used as a raw material (Saleem et al., 2022).

251 The fermentation of 10%-H and 15%-H resulted in similar LA yields (0.90 ± 0.02 g/g
252 and $0.89 \pm < 0.01$ g/g, respectively) and LA production started at early fermentation times (Fig
253 3a, b). On the other hand, as shown in Fig. 3c, in the fermentation of 20%-H, a slight delay in

254 LA production was observed. In this case, LA production started after 18 h of process
255 concomitantly with xylose consumption by *B. coagulans*. Despite this delay, a very high LA
256 yield was reached in 20%-H fermentation (0.98 ± 0.05 g/g) demonstrating for the first time the
257 suitability of PP for being used as feedstock for LA production. It is worth mentioning that
258 xylitol was negligible at these conditions, indicating that all xylose in the media was diverted
259 for LA production by *B. coagulans*.

260 Bioethanol and LA yields obtained in this study are in the range, or even slightly
261 higher, than those previously obtained by *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20
262 when individually used for bioethanol or LA from lignocellulose (Tomás-Pejó et al., 2009;
263 Cubas-Cano et al., 2020b). Thus, demonstrating that the proposed co-cultivation strategy is an
264 efficient way to simultaneously target several bioproducts. In this sense, these results pointed
265 at the proposed strategy, in which two microorganisms were co-inoculated, as an effective
266 way of valorizing PP and simultaneously producing bioethanol and LA at very high yields.

267 4. Conclusions

268 The co-inoculation of *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 and *B. coagulans* A20 resulted in
269 higher bioethanol and LA titers than the sequential inoculation. The expected positive effect
270 of oxygen depletion during bioethanol production on subsequent LA fermentation was not
271 observed. Thus, results pointed at synergistic interactions between microorganisms to explain
272 the beneficial effect of co-inoculation. The efficient bioethanol and LA simultaneous
273 generation from PP were demonstrated reaching 93 % and 98 % of the theoretical maximum
274 bioethanol and LA, respectively.

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368 FIGURE CAPTIONS

370 Figure 1. Fermentation of YPDX media with co-inoculation (a, c, e) and sequential inoculation
371 (b, d, f) of *K. marxianus* and *B. coagulans*. pH 5 (a, b), 6 (c, d) and 7 (e, f). The dotted lines
372 show *B. coagulans* inoculation time.

373 Figure 2. Drop tests on YPD plates of samples from *K. marxianus*-*B. coagulans* co-culture (Km
374 + Bc) and *K. marxianus* monoculture (Km) at 120 h of fermentation. A: 5µL drops; B: 10 µL
375 drops

376 Figure 3. Time course of bioethanol and LA co-production with co-inoculated microorganisms
377 in PPs derived hydrolysates from: a) 10 % w/w PPs; b) 15 % w/w PPs c) 20 % w/w PPs.

378

BIOETHANOL AND LACTIC ACID CO-PRODUCTION

POMEGRANATE PEELS
HYDROLYSATE

ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS OF
POMEGRANATE PEELS

K. marxianus CECT 10875
B. coagulans A20
CO-INOCULATION

SYNTHETIC MEDIA

K. marxianus CECT 10875

SEQUENTIAL INOCULATION

VS

K. marxianus CECT 10875
B. coagulans A20

CO-INOCULATION